

Intonation patterns of Estonian compound words and noun phrases in different focus conditions

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Abstract

This paper presents results from a pilot study investigating prosodic characteristics of Estonian compound words as compared to phonemically identical noun phrases. Intonation patterns over these two types in three different focus conditions are analysed. There is considerable variation as to the realisation of f_0 but some clear patterns of occurrence emerge depending on the type of word (compound or phrase) and focus (broad or contrastive on the first or second component) as well as speaker preferences.

Introduction

A major impetus to this study was a paper by Virkkunen, Šimko, Kallio, & Vainio (2018) that presented a comparison of the prosodic features of phonemically identical but semantically different Finnish compound words (CW) and noun phrases (NP) such as e.g. *kissan-kello* (harebell) vs. *kissan kello* (cat's bell) in three focus conditions. Their results showed a clear difference in the realisation of CWs and NPs in the broad focus condition (single-peaked vs. double-peaked contours) whereas the only difference between these word types in the two narrow focus conditions was in syllable duration.

In the preparation of a similar study for Estonian a pilot study was carried out of word pairs that are phonemically similar but carry a different meaning depending on whether they are a CW or a NP. As in Finnish, compounds in Estonian are orthographically written as one word and similar NPs as two words, e.g.

hiirekõrvad (birch buds) vs. *hiire kõrvad* (mouse ears).

Fujisaki & Lehiste (1982) showed that compound adjectives, e.g. *hele-kollane* (light yellow) formed one intonation phrase, whereas a sequence of two similar noncompound words, e.g. *hele, kollane* (bright, yellow) were separated by a phrase boundary. Likewise it was demonstrated by Asu, Lippus, Pajusalu, & Teras (2016, p. 157) that in most cases compounds and single-stemmed words with four and five syllables formed one intonational unit with the f_0 peak (H^*) located in the first syllable carrying the primary stress and a fall to a low target in the following syllables; in noncompound sequences the accentuation of the words depended on the intonation of the utterance.

The most common intonational pitch accent in Estonian is H^*+L (Asu, 2004) and another frequently occurring accent is $H+L^*$, where a low accented syllable is preceded by a high unaccented syllable (Asu & Nolan, 2007). The occurrence of these two pitch accents is not dependent on different focus types as information structural categories have not been found to correlate with pitch accent type in Estonian (Sahkai & Mihkla, 2017).

Based on this earlier research we expect CWs in broad focus to form one prosodic unit with accentuation on the first syllable, while in NPs both words receive an accent. In the case of narrow focus, accentuation is expected to occur on the focussed component. We expect the occurrence of both H^*+L and $H+L^*$ pitch accents but the majority of accents being H^*+L .

Material and methods

The methodology of the study follows largely that of Virkkunen et al. (2018) which would enable a direct comparison of the results for these two closely related Finnic languages in the future.

Test materials

The set of materials comprised 10 CWs and structurally similar NPs consisting of four syllables (2 syllables + 2 syllables). There were three test words where both components were in Quantity 1 (Q1): *kure + mari* (cranberry/stork's berry), *jala + vari* (footware/foot's shadow), *hane + rohi* (goose-grass/goose's medicine), and seven words where both components were in Quantity 2 (Q2). The Q2 test words included three with the CVVCV + CVCCVC structure: *hiire + kõrvad* (birch buds/mouse ears), *pääsu + silmad* (bird's eye primroses/swallow's eyes), *mooni/Mooni* (proper name) + *rullid* (poppy seed rolls/Mooni's rolls), and four with the CVCCV + CVCCVC structure: *härja + silmad* (fried eggs/ox's eyes), *varsa + kabjad* (marsh marigolds/calf's hooves), *lambi + varjud* (lamp shades/shadows of a lamp), *konna + silmad* (corns (on the foot)/frog's eyes). The test words were placed in carrier sentences utterance finally as answers to questions eliciting either broad or narrow focus on the test word or part of the test word.

Subjects and recording procedure

Three female speakers of Standard Estonian (mean age 33) participated in this pilot study. The recordings were carried out in the sound-treated recording booth of the Phonetics Laboratory at the University of Tartu. A script with the Praat Demo window (Boersma & Weenink, 2019) was used for presenting the stimuli. The subjects heard a question and saw a picture on the screen. The question was also written above the picture. The subjects had to answer the question using the wording that appeared under the

picture while the desired focus was not indicated in writing in any way. For instance, for eliciting broad focus the subjects heard and saw the question: *Mis on sellel pildil?* (What is in this picture?) after which they were prompted with an answer depending on the picture as either: *Sellel pildil on härjasilmad* (In this picture there are fried eggs) or *Sellel pildil on härja silmad* (In this picture there are ox's eyes). For the elicitation of contrastive focus on the first component the question for CWs was: *Kas sellel pildil on konnasilmad?* (Are there (foot)corns in this picture?), and for NPs: *Kas sellel pildil on koera silmad?* (Are there dog's eyes in this picture?). For the elicitation of contrastive focus on the second component the question for CWs was: *Kas sellel pildil on härjapead?* (Are there ox-heads in this picture?), and for NPs: *Kas sellel pildil on härja kõrvad?* (Are there ox ears in this picture?).

There were in total 60 questions (2 word types x 3 focus conditions x 10 test words) that appeared in random order. The subjects were given three seconds to answer each question.

Analysis

The sound files were automatically segmented using the Tallinn University of Technology forced aligner (Alumäe, Tilk, & Ullah, 2018) and the boundaries were manually corrected. Intonation of the target words was labelled phonologically using the Autosegmental Metrical intonational transcription for Estonian (Asu, 2004). Focus errors (7) and answers that did not fit the given time frame (3) were excluded. In total 170 answers were included in the analysis.

Results

Broad focus

As seen in Figure 1 four intonation patterns were used for broad focus: a contour with a peak on the first component

Figure 1. Intonation patterns and their number of occurrence for compound words (CW, green, solid line) and noun phrases (NP, blue, dashed line) in the broad focus condition. The vertical line in the middle of the box with the intonation contour marks the word boundary.

(H^*+L 0), a double-peaked contour (H^*+L H^*+L), a contour with the low accent on the first word ($H+L^*$ 0), and a sequence of two $H+L^*$ accents.

The most common pattern for CWs was a single $H+L^*$ on the first stressed component of the compound (16) followed by the single-peaked pattern shown in panel b (8). These patterns were not used with NPs (except in one case).

NPs were most often produced with the sequence of two $H+L^*$ accents as seen in panel c (17) but also with the double-peaked contour in panel d (9).

Figure 2. Intonation patterns and their number of occurrence for compound words (CW, green, solid line) and noun phrases (NP, blue, dashed line) with the narrow focus on the first component.

Narrow focus

Narrow focus on the first component

Figure 2 presents the two intonation patterns that were used in order to contrastively focus the first component of a CW and NP. The single-peaked contour was the preferred choice for both word types (panel a). For CWs, the pattern with a single $H+L^*$ was almost as frequent (14), whereas for NPs it occurred just 9 times.

Narrow focus on the second component

Different intonation patterns were used for focussing the second component (see Figure 3). The most common pattern for CWs was the one where the H^*+L accent appeared on the second component (10), followed by the sequence of two $H+L^*$ pitch accents (7) and the double-peaked contour (6). Additionally, there were also four occurrences of the $H+L^*$ 0 pattern that are not represented in the figure. These were all uttered by the same speaker.

For NPs the most common pattern was the sequence of two $H+L^*$ pitch accents. The double-peaked contour was the second most frequently used contour for NPs. The single-peaked contour on the second component appeared only three times.

Figure 3. Three most frequent intonation patterns and their number of occurrence for compound words (CW, green, solid line) and noun phrases (NP, purple, dashed line) with the narrow focus on the second component.

Discussion

The intonational analysis of compound words and identical noun phrases revealed a wide intonational variation, which was somewhat unexpected with the view of the results from the Finnish study (Virkkunen, Šimko, Kallio, & Vainio, 2018) where the intonation patterns were much more uniform. This uniformity might, however, hide a wider variation as no similar intonational analysis was conducted for the Finnish data.

As predicted, CWs mostly formed one prosodic unit whereas NPs were treated as a sequence of two words. This is indicated, for instance, by the preference of patterns containing one pitch accent for CWs and two accents for NPs in broad focus, where the frequency of occurrence of the patterns clearly depends on the word type.

The use of low accentuation (H+L*) as a focus marker to such a large extent (more occurrences than for H*+L) was not expected. As shown earlier (e.g. Asu & Nolan, 2007; Sakhai & Mihkla, 2017) the distribution of this pitch accent varies between speakers. In this data, too,

the occurrence of H+L* was extremely speaker-specific. One of the speakers had a clear preference for patterns containing H+L*. Of her 58 tokens 49 included either a single H+L* or a sequence of two H+L* pitch accents.

Interestingly, the use of low accentuation patterns seemed to be in inverse relationship with the use of the double-peaked contour: the data of the speaker who had a preference for patterns with H+L* did not include any double-peaked contours. Another speaker who had the fewest H+L* patterns produced the most double-peaked contours, and was the only speaker who used the double-peaked contour for marking broad focus. Clearly, more data from more speakers would help to shed further light on the issue of intonational speaker preferences in marking different types of focus.

Conclusions

The current pilot study investigated intonational variation in Estonian compound words and segmentally identical but semantically different noun phrases in three different focus conditions. Several intonational differences between CWs and NPs emerged, which can partly be attributed to specific speaker-preferences.

A large-scale study with more subjects is planned also addressing other prosodic features of CWs as compared to NPs including intensity, vowel and syllable duration, and syllable ratios in order to pinpoint further distinguishing characteristics between compounds and noun phrases.

References

- Alumäe, T., Tilk, O., & Ullah, A. (2018). Advanced Rich Transcription System for Estonian Speech. *Frontiers in Artificial Intelligence and Applications*, 1–8. <https://doi.org/10.3233/978-1-61499-912-6-1>
- Asu, E. L. (2004). *The phonetics and phonology of Estonian intonation*

- (Ph.D. thesis). University of Cambridge.
- Asu, E. L., Lippus, P., Pajusalu, K., & Teras, P. (2016). *Eesti keele hääldus*. Tartu Ülikooli Kirjastus.
- Asu, E. L., & Nolan, F. (2007). The analysis of low accentuation in Estonian. *Language and Speech*, 50(4), 567–588. <https://doi.org/10.1177/00238309070500040401>
- Boersma, P., & Weenink, D. (2019). Praat: doing phonetics by computer (Version 6.0.50). Retrieved from <http://www.praat.org>
- Fujisaki, H., & Lehiste, I. (1982). Some temporal and tonal characteristics of declarative sentences in Estonian. In *Preprints of Papers for the Working Group on Intonation The XIIIth International Congress of Linguists, Tokyo, 1982* (pp. 121–130).
- Sahkai, H., & Mihkla, M. (2017). Intonation of Contrastive Topic in Estonian. *Interspeech 2017*, 3181–3185. <https://doi.org/10.21437/Interspeech.2017-840>.
- Virkkunen, P., Šimko, J., Kallio, H., & Vainio, M. (2018). *Prosodic features of Finnish compound words*. 878–882. <https://doi.org/10.21437/SpeechProsody.2018-177>.